

Unpacking team age structure: Temporal evolution and its relation to team impacts

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Abstract

An understanding of the age structure of scientific teams is important in the era of global aging. Age-based characteristics of teams determine the complementarity of skills and resources, team power and diversity, and division of labor, which shapes team efficiencies and thus team performance. However, the literature on age structure in scientific teams, and its relation to team performance is scant. Based on 54 million research articles published between 1970 and 2019 in MAG, this study provides the first historical large-scale analysis of age structure in scientific teams and its association with team performance from two dimensions, i.e., seniority and age diversity, in the past half-century, in engineering, natural sciences, medicine and biology, and social sciences. We observe the increasingly aging and diverse scientific teams over years across fields and team sizes of different levels. For most categories, mean age and age Gini have an inverted-U-shaped relationship with papers' citations in a ten-year time window. Furthermore, in most disciplines, after controlling mean age and age pattern, a flat or homogeneous age structure that is characterized by a low age Gini is related to higher team impacts. The findings of this study provide implications for the practice of team formation and team management in science.

Introduction

Since the second half of the 20th century, contemporary science has been characterized by increasing reliance on teamwork (Larivière, Gingras, Sugimoto, & Tsou, 2015). The past decades have witnessed a fundamental shift from individual efforts to scientific collaboration in the production of new knowledge (Wuchty, Jones, & Uzzi, 2007). For example, single-authored papers and team-authored papers shared the same proportion in 1955 in the fields of science and engineering, while the fraction of team-authored work increased to 90% nowadays (Cooke & Hilton, 2015). The rising complexity and specialization of scientific research (Jones, 2009), and the increasing capital investment to science (Stephan, 2012), have nurtured the environment that encourages the growing prevalence of scientific collaboration. In parallel with the rise in the number of multi-authored papers, team size has grown continuously. High-impact scientific discoveries, and even scientific breakthroughs, such as Nobel Prizes research, are results of scientific collaboration (Wuchty et al., 2007; Zuckerman, 1967). Against these backdrops, the generation of new knowledge and innovation are increasingly shaped by the collective factors concerning the structure and dynamics of research teams. One of the main tasks for studies on team science is to find effective solutions for team assembly and thereby enhance team performance. To achieve a common target, scientists of different attributes, ranging from demographic characteristics, such as genders (Boschini & Sjögren, 2007), age, races (Freeman & Huang, 2015), nationalities (Wagner, Whetsell, & Mukherjee, 2019), and cultural backgrounds to cognitive ones, e.g., personalities and research interests, formed teams

and work together. To reveal effective team assembly, prior literature has extensively investigated the mechanism by which scientists of different characteristics formed teams, and how those mechanisms determined team success (Milojević, 2014; Petersen, 2015).

Age structure is one of the most prominent characteristics of team structure, and ultimately influences team success. In a variety of domains, age is considered a key driver for both individual performance and team performance. The aging process is an important determinant of individuals' physical and mental capacities, which in turn shape their competitive performance and team performance. This point has been widely embraced in various fields, such as sports, (Schulz & Curnow, 1988). Traditional wisdom suggests that the young person outperforms the older. In sports, young players are considered stronger and faster. Science is viewed as a young person's game as well because many scientific breakthroughs were created when scientists are very young. Similarly, ageism is a growing issue in high-tech industries. The average age of employees is only 29 years old in Google, and similarly in other tech companies, versus the median age of US workers which reached 42.4 in 2013.¹ If the young person is more competitive than the older one, intuitively, teams that include young team members should perform the best as well. On the contrary, others argue that teams with mixed-age team members should outperform those with either all young members or all old members due to the need for team members of different ages who could perform different tasks and contribute to different skills. The seniority of authors was found to play different roles in knowledge production, as young scientists are often engaged in technical tasks, such as experiment realization, and senior scientists make more conceptual contributions, such as research design (Larivière et al., 2016).

The paradox between the traditional wisdom and the observations leads to an inquiry about the optimal age structure, which has attracted substantial attention of researchers in a variety of fields, ranging from sports (Timmerman, 2000), management, and psychology to organizational science (De Meulenaere, Boone, & Buyl, 2016; Kilduff, Angelmar, & Mehra, 2000; Kunze, Boehm, & Bruch, 2011). In this study, we focus on how the age structure of scientific teams shapes team performance. The answer to this question is crucial for several reasons. Age is one of the most important demographic attributes of scientists (Cole, 1979; Harvey C. Lehman, 1953; Sugimoto, Sugimoto, Tsou, Milojević, & Larivière, 2016). Given the growing prevalence of teamwork in science, knowledge of the optimal age structure of scientific teams has substantial value for effective team formation and the improvement of team performance. In addition, evidence showed that scientists have been constantly aging (Jones, 2009; Matthews, Calhoun, Lo, & Ho, 2011; Sugimoto et al., 2016) and thus it is of great significance to maintaining effective age structure of teams conditioning on the inevitably increasing seniority of the whole scientific labor force.

Despite the importance of age structure in scientific teams and various efforts to investigate the link between age and individuals' scientific achievement, there is a clear gap in our knowledge of age structure in scientific teams, especially how age structure shapes team performance. Moreover, large-scale exploration of the trends in age structure of scientific teams across all disciplines and over long periods is still in its infancy.

To address the research gaps, we look into two aspects of the age structure of scientific teams, mean age and age diversity of team members that could reflect variations in age structure. The mean age of team members indicates the average degree to which scientific teams can access

¹ <https://qz.com/390835/google-age-discrimination/>

knowledge, skills, experiences, and other research resources, and the average level of motivation, creativity capacities and other factors that influence team performance. Age diversity refers to not only how diverse knowledge, and other research resources scientific teams could access to are, but also the degree to which team members generate conflicts, costs of communication and coordination caused by divergent team members. The mean age of authors in an article team is measured by the average academic age of authors in a paper, and the age diversity of members in a team is measured by the Gini coefficient.

We address the following four research questions in the pursuit of a crystal and comprehensive understanding of age structure in scientific teams by focusing on mean age and age diversity.

RQ1. How has the age structure of scientific teams evolved by periods;

RQ2. What is the association between age structure and team impact;

To solve the above-stated research questions, first, based on the MAG dataset that covers, we provide a comprehensive introduction to the evolution of mean age, and age diversity of scientific teams with a special focus on the temporal differences and disciplinary differences in age structure. Furthermore, we investigate how mean age and age diversity influence team performance solely and collectively. Mean age and age diversity are generally correlated with each other. High age diversity is related to larger mean age. To disentangle the complex relationship between these two factors, first we explore how mean age is linked to team success by controlling age diversity, and then investigate the association between age diversity by controlling mean age, to capture the sole impact of mean age or age diversity on team success. Subsequently, taking together mean age and age diversity, we probe the collective effect of mean age and age diversity on team success.

This study makes novel contributions to existing literature from multiple dimensions. This study enriches our knowledge of team assembly and team success from the perspective of age structure, which is often missing in previous literature. The angle of age structure facilitates helps fill the gap. Furthermore, from a practical perspective, the investigation of the age structure of scientific teams, and its relationship with team success, is especially meaningful against the backdrop of the aging of the scientific workforce.

The remainder of this study is organized as follows. The next section provides a discussion on the relevant literature that investigates team diversity and team performance, age and research performance, and age diversity and team success. Section 3 presents detailed introduction to data and methodology, followed by section 4 that shows the major results of this study. The last section concludes with major findings and implications.

Literature review

In this section, we review three strands of relevant studies concerning age structure in science, age and scientific performance, age diversity and team success, and important contextual factors. The question of the optimal age structure of scientific teams is concerning two questions as mentioned earlier, with one whether young scientists are more productive than their older colleagues, and another whether team diversity improves team performance. We start with a discussion on the previous studies on the relationship between age and research performance, then introduce the link between team diversity and team performance, and wrap up with important contextual factors that might shape the relationship between age structure and team performance. Overall, despite various investigations of the above-stated aspects, how scientists of different ages should be assembled for optimal team performance remains unclear.

Age and research performance

Aging is an important determinant of scientists' creativity, productivity and collaboration patterns (Sugimoto et al., 2016). The aging phenomenon has been widely observed in science across different domains, from diverse perspectives and based on various sets of data. Evidence shows that the faculty of US universities is aging due to the low rates of retirement and slowed rates of growth in enrolment in higher education, which is often known as the "greying effect" (Levin & Stephan, 1989). Researchers provided rich evidence on aging in science and discussed the consequences of aging. Jones (2009) found growth of the age at which inventors produced their first patents by investigating a dataset that includes 2.9 million utility patents issued by the US Patent and trademark office from 1963 to 1999. Analyzing the data on 544 Nobel laureates and 286 great inventors, Jones (2010) further observed that the average age at which Nobel Prize winners and great inventors made their great achievements increased by six years in the 20th century. The upward trend of age at great achievement was further attributed to both an aging population and a delay at the start of the life cycle by the authors. Evidence shows that scientists with Ph.D. degree received their first NIH grant at the age of 34.4 on average in 1970, while this figure increased to 41.7 in 2004 (Science, 2008). Besides the US, the trend of aging in science has been observed in other countries. Empirical evidence indicates that the average age of university professors in Canada grew by 7 from 1976 to 1998. However, some researchers showed a decreasing age in contrast to the age phenomena. An empirical study that investigated 19,687 Swedish inventors, showed a growing trend of age until 1997 for both all and first-time innovators, while it further found a surprisingly decreasing trend of age after that point. The authors attributed this decline in inventors' mean age to the burden of dynamic knowledge renewal for the incumbent inventors, new technological opportunities and the increasing preferences of patenting.

Aging in science is inevitable, and there is a bunch of studies on how age is related to research performance, especially an age at which scientists are most prolific or creative, or produced the most important scientific breakthrough during their academic careers. The results of previous studies on the link between age and research performance, or the age of great scientific achievement are mixed, and vary based on disciplines, countries of authors, and cohorts of scientists. Despite the mixed results, most existing research found that productivity peaks around the middle of a career (Gonzalez-Brambila & Veloso, 2007; Jones, 2009; Harvey Christian Lehman, 2017; Dean Keith Simonton, 1988). Psychologists, sociologists and economists demonstrated the reasons for the shape concerning the relationship between age and research productivity from diverse perspectives. The curvilinear relationship is caused by changes in cognitive and psychological capacities (Lawrence & Blackburn, 1985), knowledge obsolescence (Kyvik & Olsen, 2008), reward system (Cole, 1979; Hagstrom, 1965; Merton, 1957) and incentives (Tien & Blackburn, 1996; L. Turner & Mairesse, 2005), during the life span.

In addition, knowledge is cumulative and experiences generally increase with seniority. According to the cumulative advantage theory, senior scientists who usually have higher academic ranks (Abramo, D'Angelo, & Di Costa, 2011), possess more intangible resources than junior ones, such as a larger stock of experiences, knowledge and competencies, more human and social capital accumulated in their past research activities (Abramo et al., 2011; Gingras, Lariviere, Macaluso, & Robitaille, 2008), and better familiarity with research topics (Puuska, 2010). However, relative to younger ones, senior scientists are disadvantaged in aspects including cognitive capacities (Giambra, Arenberg, Zonderman, Kawas, & Costa Jr, 1995), the risks of knowledge obsolescence (Kyvik & Olsen, 2008), and a loss of research

interests (Phelan, 1994). Junior scientists have advantages as well. Many scientists, such as Gauss, Charles Darwin, Albert Einstein and Isaac Newton, produced their greatest research achievement at a young age. These examples lead to a popular belief in science that young scientists might be more creative and are more likely to generate novel research ideas. Early psychological research showed that intellectual abilities generally decline with time, especially after age 60 (Doppelt & Wallace, 1955; K. Schaie, 1994; K. W. Schaie, 1958). In the field of the psychology of science, Simonton documented the most influential theory concerning the association of age, cognitive ability and scientific achievement. He proposed a quantitative model that predicts a curvilinear relationship between career age and research productivity. From Simonton's theory, the utility-maximizing theory suggests that to junior scientists have stronger incentives to publish than senior ones by spending more effort on research because they are more rewarded for new achievements than their elder colleagues (Kyvik, 1990; Rey-Rocha, Garzón-García, & Martín-Sempere, 2006). Besides, facing the pressure caused by "publish or perish", young scientists are more driven to publish to secure tenure and promotion (Lissoni, Mairesse, Montobbio, & Pezzoni, 2011).

Probably due to the well-known fact that many important scientific breakthroughs have been made by young scientists, there is a long-standing belief that scientists' biological age is negatively associated with performance indicators, such as productivity, creativity and scientific impacts, which has been supported by early studies (Harvey C. Lehman, 1953; Dean K Simonton, 1988). Analyzing the data on labs of the Italian National Research Council, researchers observed a negative correlation between the average age of researchers and research institutes' productivity, which holds across different scientific areas (Bonaccorsi & Daraio, 2002).

However, distinctive from the early literature described above, most relevant literature suggested a quadratic association between age and research performance. Productivity grows with the increase in scientists' seniority until a turning point, and then drops with scientists' aging. Despite mixed results regarding the relationship between scientists' age and productivity, most existing research found that productivity peaks around the middle of a career (Gonzalez-Brambila & Veloso, 2007; Jones, 2009; Harvey Christian Lehman, 2017; Dean Keith Simonton, 1988). This curvilinear relationship is caused by changes in cognitive abilities, reward system (Cole, 1979) and motivations, during the life span. An empirical analysis of data on scientists in six different disciplines that include chemistry, geology, mathematics, physics, psychology and sociology, suggested that age is curvilinearly related to the quantity and quality of research outputs (Cole, 1979). He observed a slight decline in scientific productivity over the fifties by investigating a cohort of mathematicians who received their Ph.D. degree between 1947 and 1950. Using a unique dataset that covers 7793 Mexican researchers from 1991 to 2001, an analysis found that scientists' productivity peaks at the age of 53 (Gonzalez-Brambila & Veloso, 2007). A study that investigates 1,064 scientists from Spanish National Research Council suggested that productivity presents an inverted U-shape association with age in biology and biomedicine, and material science, while a negative link with age in natural resources (Costas, van Leeuwen, & Bordons, 2010). The authors further found that the oldest scientists showed the lowest productivity. Studying the publication history of more than one thousand authors in sociology, economics and political science from highly ranked US institutions, Sugimoto et al. (2016) demonstrated that researchers' productivity increased sharply until they were promoted to associate professors, and remained steady. The authors further found that authors' citation impacts peaked around 4-12 years after they are awarded Ph.D. degrees. Australian researchers obtained the most citations per publication at the

academic ages of 10 to 29, evidenced by an analysis of researchers in three sampled Australian universities (Gu & Blackmore, 2017).

In contrast, some recent empirical studies did not find a clear link between age and the production of great scientific achievement. Using survey data that covers 12 reputational researchers in information science, Cronin and Meho (2007) found that the sampled researchers were not most creative during their early career stages, but remain productive throughout their careers (Cronin & Meho, 2007). An analysis of chemists and physicists found no relevance between age and scientists' high-impact research as scientists' influential publications are distributed randomly within academic careers (Sinatra, Wang, Deville, Song, & Barabási, 2016). A recent investigation of large-scale career histories of artists, scientists and film directors, showed that a specific period during which scientists' performance is far better than their typical performance, that is known as hot streaks, could occur randomly across scientists' academic careers (L. Liu et al., 2018).

Age diversity and team performance

Age diversity indicates the distribution of differences among team members regarding age. Research on the age diversity of teams is built upon two competing theories: social categorization theory (Tajfel, 1981; J. C. Turner, Hogg, Oakes, Reicher, & Wetherell, 1987), and the information-processing perspective (Mannix & Neale, 2005; Phillips & O'Reilly, 1998). These two theories suggest that age diversity is a double-edged sword for team performance. The existing empirical literature also yields contradictory results on how age diversity is related to team performance, as well as the extent to which assembling scientists of different ages can improve team performance.

The perspective of social categorization suggests a negative effect of age diversity on team performance due to intergroup bias that disrupts collective teamwork (Brewer & Kramer, 1985). Social categorization theory documents that people naturally tend to categorize individuals into certain groups with similar attributes, such as gender, race, nationality, age and so forth (Tajfel, 1981; J. C. Turner et al., 1987). Such social categorization leads to the stereotyping of others (Fiske, Cuddy, Glick, & Xu, 2002), age discrimination (Kunze et al., 2011; Shore & Goldberg, 2013), worse cohesion and social integration, more age-related conflicts and communication and coordination problems, less cooperation with others caused by the dissimilarity between team members (Carton & Cummings, 2012; van Dijk & van Engen, 2013; Van Dijk, Van Engen, & Van Knippenberg, 2012). These negative experiences that are triggered by age diversity will weaken the relationship between team members (Boehm & Kunze, 2015), impede the elaboration of task-related information (Van Knippenberg, De Dreu, & Homan, 2004) and ultimately hamper team performance. A few empirical studies provide evidence that is in line with this point of view (Kunze et al., 2011; Timmerman, 2000).

The perspective of information and decision-making, suggests a positive effect of age diversity on team performance due to the complementarity regarding resources between scientists of different ages. The categorization-elaboration model suggests that team performance could be improved by exchanging, discussing and integrating divergent ideas, knowledge and perspectives that are related to teams' tasks (Kearney, Gebert, & Voelpel, 2009). For example, younger scientists often contribute more to technical tasks, while senior ones focus more on the big picture and "conceptual" tasks (Larivière et al., 2016). Thus, the combination of both young and senior scientists facilitates the achievement of research goals that might incorporate diverse kinds of tasks. Age-diverse scientists are different in cognitive, affective and behavioural aspects, as discussed in the former section. Age diversity allows broader access to task-relevant

knowledge, information, skills and capacities, and thus facilitates task accomplishment and team performance (Schneid, Isidor, Steinmetz, & Kabst, 2016). Furthermore, team members from different age cohort groups possessed distinctive work and life experiences (Kunze et al., 2011), which leads to more variance in task-related ideas and problem-solving abilities (Kearney et al., 2009). Due to the heterogeneity of team members discussed above, some researchers argued that age diversity could lead to desirable team outcomes. This is because age diversity reflects complementary knowledge, skills, experiences, information and other resources among team members that help teams more effectively perform various tasks (Grant, 1996; Li et al., 2021). Furthermore, the socioemotional selectivity theory implies complementarity concerning social connections between young and older team members. This theory suggests an age-associated shift in time perspective that influence individuals' decision to achieve two goals: knowledge-related goals and emotion-related goals. Young people normally perceive their future as open-ended, and thus might build a broader range of social connections that are beneficial for their career development and knowledge gathering, while older people might tend to narrow social interactions and focus more on close and targeted social connections (Burmeister, Wang, & Hirschi, 2020; M. Wang, Burlacu, Truxillo, James, & Yao, 2015). In this sense, age-diverse scientists could establish complementary social ties that help teams acquire complementary internal and external connections. Therefore, due to the complementarity concerning various types of academic resources, the mixing of team members of different ages could stimulate team creativity, innovative solutions and other team performance indicators (Bantel & Jackson, 1989; De Meulenaere et al., 2016; Hammermann, Niendorf, & Schmidt, 2019). This argument has been supported by a few empirical studies (Ilmakunnas & Ilmakunnas, 2011; Kilduff et al., 2000).

However, a few studies found no or weak connection between age diversity on team performance. As reviewed earlier, age diversity could improve or hinder team performance through various mechanisms. It is possible that the promoting and detrimental effects could cancel each other and thus the link between age diversity and team performance might be weak (Gellert & Kuipers, 2008; Schneid et al., 2016).

Besides the linear association discussed above, some studies demonstrated that the relationship between age diversity and team performance follows an inverted-U shape. Some researchers argued that the extremes of age diversity could lead to low team performance since either the resources teams could access to are too homogeneous or conflicts and coordination problems are too prominent. For example, a study that investigates 7,000 Danish firms from 1992 to 1997, and found that mean age and age dispersion in firms are inversely U-shaped associated with firm performance (Grund & Westergaard-Nielsen, 2008).

Data and methods

Data source

The major data source is the MAG dataset that covers publications and provides related information including document type, authors, venue, the field of publications, publication year and so forth. It also provides the citation relationships between publications. We only focus on journal articles with more than one author. We only analyze non-humanities and art publications from 1970 to 2019. The final dataset in this study includes roughly 54 million journal articles that cover four categories and 16 sub-disciplines. The distribution of document types and that of disciplines in MAG are shown in Fig S1 and S2 in Appendix. There are some limitations of MAG dataset. MAG shows biases regarding the coverage of humanities, non-English publications. In MAG, the metadata of some publications does not include all authors. Besides, MAG also shows sparsity in the early years.

Measures of mean age and age diversity of scientific teams

We use scientists' academic age (Milojević, 2012) that is defined the number of years collapsed from their first publications in MAG until the publication year of the focal paper. The mean age of authors in an article team is measured by the average academic age of authors in a paper. Following prior literature that measures age diversity using the Gini coefficient (He & Huang, 2011), we use this index to measure age diversity level in teams. A larger Gini coefficient indicates a higher level of diversity. The Gini coefficient ranges between 0 and 1, with zero indicating fully homogeneous, and with one referring to maximally diverse.

Gini coefficient is the most common statistical index of diversity in terms of continuous variables among a variety of indices used in previous literature, such as variance (Pielou, 1977), the coefficient of variation (Allison, 1978; Bedeian & Mossholder, 2000), the standard deviation (Hammermann et al., 2019). The Gini coefficient is originally proposed to measure income or wealth inequality (Nayak & Gastwirth, 1989) (Cerqueti & Ausloos, 2015). In recent years, the Gini coefficient was applied in information science, to quantify diversity concerning important components of research articles at different levels, such as the diversity of papers' knowledge integration (that is known as interdisciplinarity) (Leydesdorff, 2018; Leydesdorff, Wagner, & Bornmann, 2019; Zhang & Leydesdorff, 2021), the complexity of technologies (Broekel, 2019), ethnical diversity of authors (AlShebli, Rahwan, & Woon, 2018), the breadth or depth in research specialization (Chien, Chow, Chang, & Chou, 2018) and so forth. For example, the Gini coefficient has been usually applied to capture unevenness and unbalance of distribution of references across disciplines in a paper (Leydesdorff & Rafols, 2011; Leydesdorff et al., 2019; J. Wang, Thijs, & Glänzel, 2015).

We calculate the age pattern of authors in each publication based on the age group each author belongs to. Authors are classified into the following four categories: junior (career age between 1 and 10), early-career (career age between 11 and 15), mid-career (career age between 16 and 20) and full-career (career age larger than 20). Based on the combination of categories the authors in a publication belong to, we measure the age pattern of authors in each publication.

Team impact is measured by the number of citations a paper received in 10 years (C10) since its publication. C10 is considered effective to quantify papers' long-term citations, and has been often used in prior literature (M. Liu, Shi, & Li, 2017; Sinatra et al., 2016; J. Wang, 2013).

A multivariable regression analysis method

We use a multivariate regression model to explore the relationship between mean age and papers' citations, and that between age diversity and papers' citations, respectively. C10 is estimated by Equation 1. Mean age is the independent variable that indicates the average career age of authors in paper i . To control for various confounding factors, three controls are incorporated into Equation 1, i.e., team size measured by the number of authors in a paper (Larivière et al., 2015; Lee, Walsh, & Wang, 2015), and the average number of publications published by the authors in the past five years, and age Gini. To control the time-invariant and discipline-invariant factors, fixed effects in terms of publication year (Y_t) and discipline (F_i) are included in Equation 1.

$$C10_i = \alpha + \beta_1(\text{Mean age}_i) + \beta_2(\text{Controls}) + F_i + Y_t + \epsilon_{it} \quad (1)$$

The link between mean age and papers' C10 is not necessarily linear, and thus we test whether there is a curvilinear association between mean age and papers' C10 by including the square term of mean age, i.e., $\text{Mean age} \times \text{Mean age}$, in Equation 1.

Similarly, we examine the association between mean age and papers' C10 by replacing $Mean\ age_i$ with $Age\ Gini_i$ in Equation 1, and including mean age as a control. The square term of age diversity, i.e., $Age\ Gini \times Age\ Gini$, is introduced to the Equation to investigate whether a non-linear relationship remains between age diversity and papers' C10. We use natural logs of the values of the variable besides age Gini.

The Descriptive statistics and Pearson correlation coefficients of variables are shown in Table 1 and Table 2, respectively.

Table 1. Descriptive statistics of variables

<i>Variable</i>	<i>Obs</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Std. dev.</i>	<i>Min</i>	<i>Max</i>
Mean age	54,807,764	1.593	1.017	0	5.347
Age Gini	54,807,764	0.3	0.198	0	0.861
Past productivity	54,807,764	1.878	1.274	0	6.943
Team size	54,807,764	1.58	0.431	1.099	8.819
C10	29,370,739	1.344	1.299	0	9.978

Notes: We use natural logs of the values of the variable besides age Gini.

Table 2. Pearson coefficient matrix

	Mean age	Age Gini	Past productivity	Team size	C10
Mean age	1				
Age Gini	0.6281	1			
Past productivity	0.7875	0.5212	1		
Team size	0.2371	0.4029	0.3232	1	
C10	0.353	0.2609	0.3339	0.1454	1

Notes: We use natural logs of the values of the variable beside age Gini.

Results

We begin by introducing the overview of the age structure of scientific teams in the past five decades with a focus on temporal and disciplinary differences. Then, the findings of the association between age structure and team impact are further presented.

The age structure in scientific teams: Mean age, age pattern and age diversity

We observe the increasingly aging and diverse scientific teams over years across fields and team sizes of different levels. As indicated in Figure 1a, in the past half a century, in general, the mean age and mean age Gini of scientific teams in engineering, medicine and biology, natural sciences and social sciences, grew constantly. The increasing trend of mean age and age Gini in the four categories are also found for team sizes of different levels (Figure 1a). It is natural to see that the average career age of members in scientific teams has constantly and significantly grown in the past half-century, since the career age of scientists started being accumulated from 1950 in this study.

The disciplinary differences are found in the median of mean age and that of age Gini. As shown in Figures 2(a) and 2(b). Generally, the age structure in social sciences is more homogeneous than that in the remaining three categories. This is because this category has a low mean age

and age Gini of team members on average. In contrast, teams in medicine and biology, and natural sciences reached the highest level of age Gini and mean age among all the categories. Although the absolute value of mean age and age Gini is not high in engineering, the annual average growth rates of the two indicators in engineering are the highest among all the categories that reached 2.65% and 3.08%, respectively (Figure 2c).

This study further explores the age pattern in scientific teams by looking at the composition of junior- (0-10 years after the first publications), early- (11-15 years after the first publications), middle- (16-20 years after the first publications) and full-career authors who have careers longer than 20 years in scientific teams. One prominent trend for all the categories is that the fraction of teams with only junior scientists continually decreased and accordingly the fraction of teams with authors of multiple age groups went up. The above evidence also indicates the increasingly diverse age structure of scientific teams.

Figure 1. The temporal evolution of age structure in scientific teams in the past five decades.

Notes: (a) the mean age and mean Gini of authors in publications across years. (b) the development of mean age and mean Gini of authors in publications across years by the quantiles of team size. (c) the fraction of different age patterns of publications across years.

Figure 2. The box plot/growth rates of mean age and age Gini of teams in four categories.

Notes: (a) and (b) EN, MB, NS and SS indicates engineering, medicine and biology, natural sciences and social sciences.

The association between age pattern and team impacts

We next investigate how the mean age and age Gini of team members influence team impacts independently. In the short term and middle term, mean age and age diversity both have positive effects on team performance, while these two aspects of age structure showed an inverted-U-shaped relationship between papers' long-term citations. By controlling age diversity and other influential factors of citations, for engineering, natural sciences and social sciences, mean age and papers' C10 have an inverted-U-shaped association (see Figure 3(a)). The inverted-U shape remains for the relationship between age diversity and papers' C10 for all four categories (see Figure 3(b)). Specifically, more diverse age compositions of teams lead to higher citations in a ten-year citation window since age diversity reaches a turning point.

Figure 2. The linear estimation regarding the association between mean age/age Gini and papers' C10.

Notes: (a) and (b) shows the estimated relationship between mean age/age Gini and papers' C10 by controlling other influential factors of papers' citations, respectively, based on Equation 1. Generally, a U-shaped association remains concerning the association between mean age/age Gini and papers' C10. The shaded area represents $\pm 1.96 * \text{std. the error of each point estimate}$. Mean age, and C10 are naturally log-transformed.

The nexus between age diversity and team impacts

Controlling mean age and age patterns of authors in a publication, we find that the links between the age Gini of teams and team impacts differ across disciplines. Generally, in a majority of disciplines, a flat or homogenous age structure of team members that is characterized by low age Gini, is related to higher team impacts. In each discipline, publications are divided into twenty groups according to the percentile of mean age of members in scientific teams. In each level of mean age, we compare papers' C10 across two groups of publications, i.e., publications with low /high age Gini. As Figure 4a shows, in engineering and social sciences, low Gini groups receive significantly more citations than high Gini groups with a similar level of mean age. It should be noted that the significant difference in C10 between groups with age Gini of different levels only exists at the medium or high levels of mean age. In other words, the citation advantage of high-Gini teams is not manifested if the mean age of team members is too small. The comparison of the mean of C10 in high Gini and low Gini groups across different disciplines is shown in Figure 5. Again, in most disciplines, teams of low Gini groups acquire higher citations. We further find that the citation advantage of flat age structure teams exists across different age patterns of team members. With the increase in age Gini, the average C10 of teams of each age pattern is decreasing (Figure 4b).

Figure 4. The relationship between age Gini of teams and papers' C10.

Notes: (a) the mean of papers' C10 in high Gini groups and low Gini groups; (b) the relationship between age Gini levels and papers' C10. The major age patterns are included.

Figure 5. The mean of papers' C10 in high Gini groups and low Gini groups across disciplines.

Notes: The x-axis indicates age Gini levels and the Y-axis indicates the mean of C10.

Discussion and conclusion

The age structure of scientific teams has been shaped by diverse historical changes in science in recent decades. The increasing aging phenomenon has been observed in a variety of domains. Against this backdrop, it is crucial to understand how age structure is related to team performance in science for the optimal age structure in teams. Focusing on the mean age and age diversity of scientific teams, we depict the landscape of the age structure of scientific teams based on 54 million research articles published between 1970 and 2019 in MAG, then explore the link between age structure and team impacts.

Papers' citations in the ten-year citation window increase with the growth of mean age and age Gini of team members until the turning points are reached. As discussed earlier, the age Gini of team members reflects the diversity of age structure in teams. Teams would lack diversified academic resources ranging from knowledge, skills, experiences to social connections, when team members are so homogenous in age. Furthermore, controlling for mean age and age pattern, in most disciplines, we observe that a flat age structure that is characterized by low age Gini is related to higher team impacts. When the age Gini is high, the dark side of age diversity, such as team conflicts, coordination problems and weakened relationship among team members, might outweigh its benefits and thus we observe that teams with low age Gini brings higher papers' citations, relative to those of high age Gini.

This study has several limitations. This study only uses a collection of authors represented on the byline of a publication as a proxy for scientific teams. However, co-authorship data cannot capture the collaboration activities of researchers who are not listed as authors of a research article.

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Appendix

Figure S3. The distribution of document types in MAG data

Figure S4. The distribution of disciplines in the MAG dataset.